

IMMUNOGENETIC DETERMINANTS OF THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL AND METABOLIC PHENOTYPES OF METABOLIC SYNDROME IN ADOLESCENTS AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NUTRICEUTICAL CORRECTION

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ABSTRACT

Metabolic syndrome (MS) in adolescents is a pressing medical and social issue in modern pediatrics and endocrinology. Early development of clinical and metabolic disorders increases the risk of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes in adulthood. In recent years, particular attention has been paid to the role of immunogenetic factors and chronic subclinical inflammation in the pathogenesis of MS, as well as the potential for its correction using nutraceuticals

Introduction. Metabolic syndrome (MS) in adolescents is a pressing medical and social issue in modern pediatrics and endocrinology. Early development of clinical and metabolic disorders increases the risk of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes in adulthood. In recent years, particular attention has been paid to the role of immunogenetic factors and chronic subclinical inflammation in the pathogenesis of MS, as well as the potential for its correction using nutraceuticals.

Purpose of the study. To study the immunogenetic determinants of the formation of clinical and metabolic phenotypes of metabolic syndrome in adolescents and evaluate the effectiveness of nutraceutical correction.

Materials and methods. Adolescents with signs of metabolic syndrome were examined. Anthropometric parameters, carbohydrate and lipid metabolism parameters, insulin resistance, systemic inflammation markers, and immune status indicators were assessed. Immunogenetic analysis included the study of gene polymorphisms associated with the inflammatory response and metabolic disorders. Treatment included the use of nutraceutical complexes with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and metabolic activity.

Results. Various clinical and metabolic phenotypes of MS in adolescents have been identified, associated with specific immunogenetic variants. The presence of pro-inflammatory genetic markers has been found to contribute to more pronounced metabolic disturbances. Nutritional interventions have been associated with improved lipid and carbohydrate metabolism, decreased inflammatory markers, and increased insulin sensitivity.

Conclusion. Immunogenetic factors play a significant role in the development of clinical and metabolic phenotypes of metabolic syndrome in adolescents. Nutritional correction can

be considered an effective and safe component of comprehensive prevention and treatment of metabolic syndrome in adolescence.

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